

Thermal-Hydraulics and Critical Boron Search Embedded in Neutronics Power Iterations

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a novel numerical scheme where the thermal-hydraulics solution, the boron concentration search and the updated macroscopic cross-sections are embedded in the transport power iterations, which are accelerated via coarse mesh finite differences (CMFD). A 3-D assembly containing UO_x fuel and B_4C control rods is simulated to assess the benefits of the scheme.

Keywords: Multiphysics, neutronics - thermal-hydraulics coupling, deterministic methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

Historically speaking, neutronics (N) and thermal-hydraulics (TH) are coupled via fixed-point iterations, in which N and TH exchange information in a black-box fashion, i.e., each physics is solved without knowing the other. Except for specific applications, where thermal-hydraulics is solved by CFD, the largest workload is generally due to the neutronics code, solving a full multigroup eigenvalue problem at each fixed-point iteration, by the end of which a converged power distribution is provided. These schemes - widely used in the past - may be affected by numerical instabilities [1] and require a high cumulative number of multigroup power iterations, typically of the order of some hundreds, for each stationary core state with N-TH at equilibrium. A vast literature is available proposing stabilized fixed point N-TH via Anderson acceleration, Jacobian-Free Newton-Krylov iterations, or Residual Minimization techniques, [2, 3], to mention some possible workarounds. Nonetheless, in none of the aforementioned methods, the two physics, i.e. N and TH, take advantage of each other. We departed from this approach to conceive a calculation strategy in which all feed-backs are embedded in CMFD-accelerated transport power iterations. The guidelines for the scheme are as follows:

1. Avoid microscopic cross-section homogenisation;
2. Perform transport simulations in real geometry;
3. Perform data decomposition in order to sub-divide the work-load relative to cross-section generation and rely on multigroup transport calculation in subdomains to ease the access to parallel computing;
4. Take profit of accelerated transport iterations, where non-linear diffusion is used as a physical preconditioner¹;
5. Reduce the memory imprint of the angular probability matrices, when temperature and depleted concentration fields are distributed over the calculation geometry.

2. THE ALGORITHM

Figure 1 illustrates the algorithm investigated in this work. The calculation scheme involves three codes developed at CEA:

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¹The coarse-mesh of the CMFD operator is used as geometrical support to discretize the thermal-hydraulics channels.

- The discrete-ordinate multigroup transport solver IDT, computing the spatial distribution of the neutron flux via the methods of short characteristics (MOSC) over the decomposed domain [4, 5];
- The macroscopic cross section generator XSTOOL, responsible for microscopic cross-section interpolation. The code does not perform cross-section homogenisation and may collapse the obtained macroscopic cross-sections to relatively few energy groups, if required;
- The multi-1D two-phase thermal-hydraulics solver THEDI, [6], here used to solve mass, momentum and energy conservation, in stationary monophasic flow over independent sub-channels, and 1D steady-state fuel heat conduction.

Figure 1. Advanced two-step scheme, embedding thermal-hydraulics and target boron concentration search in neutron transport iterations, preconditioned by non-linear diffusion.

As mentioned, the implemented strategy consists in integrating the boron concentration update and the thermal-hydraulic solution within the power iterations. Using the integer ℓ as the fixed-point iteration index, C_B as the boron concentration and $\Theta = (T_f, T_m, \rho_m)$ as the vector containing the thermal fields, the N-TH coupled equations are solved iteratively within a single loop as follows,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 \text{Multigroup-transport (XSTOOL+IDT):} \\
 \mathbf{B}(C_B^{(\ell)}, \Theta^{(\ell)})\psi^{(\ell+1/2)} = \frac{1}{\lambda^{(\ell)}} \mathbf{F}(C_B^{(\ell)}, \Theta^{(\ell)})\psi^{(\ell)}; \\
 \text{CMFD solver (IDT):} \\
 \mathbf{A}(\psi^{(\ell+1/2)})\phi^{CMFD} = \frac{1}{\lambda_{CMFD}} \mathbf{F}(\psi^{(\ell+1/2)})\phi^{CMFD}; \\
 \text{Eigenvalue, flux and power update (IDT):} \\
 \lambda^{(\ell+1)} = \lambda_{CMFD} \\
 \psi^{(\ell+1)} = \psi^{(\ell+1/2)} \frac{\phi^{CMFD}}{\int \psi^{(\ell+1/2)}}; \quad P^{(\ell+1)} = \left(\int k_{fiss} \Sigma_f \phi \right)^{CMFD} \\
 \text{Boron update (IDT):} \\
 C_B^{(\ell+1)} = C_B^{(\ell)} + \left(\frac{C_B^{(\ell)} - C_B^{(\ell-1)}}{k^{(\ell+1)} - k^{(\ell)}} \right) (k_{ref} - k^{(\ell+1)}); \\
 \text{TH solver (THEDI):} \\
 \Theta^{(\ell+1)} = \mathbf{T}(P^{(\ell+1)}).
 \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

The thermal feedback and the updated macroscopic cross-section library are provided by THEDI and XSTOOL, respectively, while neutron transport is simulated by IDT. The microscopic cross sections are generated purely on the basis of the *External Reference Library*, provided by GALILEE [7], and of the *External Parametric Library of Shelf-Shielding factors* (EPL-SSH), without preliminary homogenisation and energy collapsing. The obtained macroscopic cross sections may be collapsed in energy, by means of a dedicated option of XSTOOL, in which the critical flux resulting from the 2-D lattice simulation, previously stored in the EPL-SSH, is used as a weighting function to reduce the number of energy groups.

IDT solves a fixed-source boundary problem over each subdomain by local multigroup transport iterations. Currents are transmitted among neighbouring subdomains, to satisfy interface flux continuity. To accelerate neutron transport, multigroup CMFD is solved by successive iterations over the whole domain, until full convergence. For this purpose, nuclear data are first homogenised over coarse spatial meshes and condensed to few energy groups. The last transport eigenpair allows to initialise the CMFD problem, which is converged by power, thermal and inner iterations, the latter being approached by the BICGStab-Krylov method. The obtained solution is used to renormalise the transport distribution and update the eigenvalue. The updated values are fed into the boron linear search algorithm and the thermal-hydraulic problem. The latter in turn, here indicated as $\Theta = \mathbf{T}(P)$, based on the new power distribution and boundary conditions, which are specified in a dedicated file, generates new temperature fields for the fuel and the moderator, as well as the updated moderator density map. At this point, the temperature and density distributions, together with the effective multiplication factor and fission integral, are compared between two successive multiphysics iterations within each subdomain and halt the iteration loop once the specified tolerance is reached.

3. STABILISATION AND CONVERGENCE CRITERIA

The target boron concentration is searched via a Newton formula, as detailed in Eq. (1). In order to prevent oscillations, no boron concentration calculation is performed until the relative error on the eigenvalue is less than 1%. If the boron concentration verifies the condition

$$|C_B^{(l+1)} - C_B^{(l)}| < C_B^{(l+1)} \cdot \epsilon_k, \quad (2)$$

ϵ_k being the tolerance on the eigenvalue, no cross-section update is triggered, unless the thermal fields have not yet converged.

The solution provided by THEDI is used to separately update the cross sections of each subdomain. In particular, the cross sections of a given subdomain are not recomputed, if the local value of the effective fuel temperature and the local value of the moderator density differ by less than ϵ_f and ϵ_m , in absolute value, with respect to the corresponding values at the prior fixed-point iteration. The tuning of such tolerances is addressed in the upcoming section.

Concerning neutronics, the error criteria over the outermost loop are defined as follows,

$$\epsilon_k = \left| 1 - \frac{k^{(l+1)}}{k^{(l)}} \right| \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_F = \left| 1 - \frac{\sum_g (F_u \psi_u^{(l+1)})^g}{\sum_g (F_u \psi_u^{(l)})^g} \right| \quad (4)$$

$$\epsilon_\psi = \left| 1 - \frac{\int_{2\pi^-} d^2\Omega |\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{\Omega}| \psi_u^{-,(l+1)}}{\int_{2\pi^-} d^2\Omega |\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{\Omega}| \psi_u^{-,(l)}} \right| \quad (5)$$

$u = 1, \dots, U$, U being the number of subdomains, as detailed in [8].

The implemented framework also exposes a regulation parameter to the user, allowing to loosen the coupling strategy, by running the thermal-hydraulic solver every \mathcal{N} power iterations, where \mathcal{N} is a positive integer. In other words, \mathcal{N} defines the number of power iterations between two successive updates of the thermal fields, which allows to partially converge the neutronic power map and k_{eff} . This entails that cross-sections and HCC's angular probability coefficients are not updated for $\mathcal{N} - 1$ iterations. The impact of this parameter on the number of iterations is substantial and a dedicated discussion is included in Sec. 4.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Let us consider a 17×17 3D assembly consisting of 0.02 cm thick water blades and 0.0194 cm thick zirconium alloy E110 spacer grids, fueled by UO_x , moderated and cooled by light water, and regulated using B_4C control rods. Mirror reflection boundary conditions are imposed on the radial edges, while vacuum boundary conditions are set on the bottom and top boundaries. The total height of the assembly is 400 cm and includes two axial reflectors (top and bottom, respectively) of 20 cm each. Control rods are inserted over the top 70 cm. The external reference library is provided by GALILEE and contains 281 energy groups. The EPL-SSH provided by APOLLO3[®] contains the self-shielding factors of the 2-D lattice representing the X-Y cross section of the unrodded part of the assembly without spacer grids. The macroscopic cross-sections are collapsed to 26 energy groups, using APOLLO3[®] TDT-MOC neutron flux, from the lattice calculation, and contain P_1 scattering matrices. No critical boron concentration search is performed in this first test.

The transport equation is solved by S_8 Chebyshev-Legendre quadrature, containing 128 angular directions. The spatial domain is subdivided into $19 \times 19 \times 40$ Heterogeneous Cartesian Cells (HCC), thus containing a total of 14440 nodes, with the water blade simulated as a distinct cell. The total number of media varies from 72868, if the whole assembly is modelled as a single thermal-hydraulic channel, up to 13696, if each channel comprises 2×2 pin-cells. The spatial solution is obtained by Linear Short Characteristics. Domain decomposition is also applied, with $3 \times 3 \times 10$ symmetrically-distributed subdomains. Concerning the error criteria, the k-eigenvalue and the fission integral are required to converge to within 1 pcm and 10 pcm, respectively, while the tolerance on the inner loop is set equal to 10 pcm.

Thermal-Hydraulics is solved under the following boundary conditions:

- Water inlet temperature, $T_{in} = 550$ K;
- Pressure, $p = 155$ MPa;
- Flow rate, $\dot{m} = 96 \frac{kg}{s}$.

The total power P_{tot} is normalized to 20 MW. The TH channel is discretized by 40 axial planes of equal size (10 cm). Fuel pin-cells heat conduction is solved using

- 4 rings for the fuel, distributed according to the following ratios: 0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1 (i.e., 40%, 30%, 20% and 10% of the total fuel radius, r_f);
- 4 rings for the helium gap, with ratios 0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1;
- 3 rings for the Zr-clad, with ratios 0.5, 0.3, 0.2.

In the following, two simulations are proposed, sharing the same set of N/TH input parameters, except for the aforementioned number \mathcal{N} , determining the frequency at which the temperature map is updated, along the outer loop. In particular, for the simulation labelled as 'Strong', \mathcal{N} is set equal to 1 (i.e., the temperature distribution is updated every outer iteration), whereas, for the simulation marked as 'Weak', \mathcal{N} is equal to 5. In reality, both tests should be qualified as 'strong', as the multigroup transport iterations are not converged before solving thermal-hydraulics to the required precision. The computational time spent to interpolate the parametric cross sections amounts, in total, to 1 min 46 s, while the

 (a) δk - wrong criterion $\frac{\delta \rho_m}{\rho_m} \leq 1\%$

 (b) δk - good criterion $\frac{\delta \rho_m}{\rho_m} \leq 1\text{ pcm}$

 Figure 2. Convergence of N -TH iterations: Strong ($\mathcal{N} = 1$) vs. Weak ($\mathcal{N} = 5$) for fully converged inner and thermal transport iterations

 Table I. Difference Strong vs Weak, tolerance on water density (ρ_m) $\leq 1\%$ vs. $\leq 1\text{ pcm}$

	$\frac{\delta \rho_m}{\rho_m} \leq 1\%$		$\frac{\delta \rho_m}{\rho_m} \leq 1\text{ pcm}$	
	strong	weak	strong	weak
k -eff	0.96416	0.96589	0.96429	0.96425
δk	-	178 pcm	-	4 pcm
$\max \delta(\mathcal{F}\psi)$	-	7%	-	0.3%

time spent to recompute the angular probability coefficients is about 8 min 6 s.

4.1. Strong vs. Weak coupling

The two calculations ('Strong' and 'Weak') are compared to each other, in order to test the convergence of the algorithm to the required precision, as the frequency of the multiphysics iterations varies along the outer loop. The numerical results are expected to be the same, with an error of the order of the required precision. The possibility to loosen the coupling strategy, from $\mathcal{N} = 1$ to $\mathcal{N} = 5$ in the presented case study, is inspired to [9, 2, 10, 3].

Concerning the stopping criteria, for the local fuel / moderator temperatures we set $\epsilon_{T_f} = 5^\circ\text{C}$ and $\epsilon_{T_m} = 1^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, whereas the tolerance for the moderator density is equal to $\epsilon_{\rho_m} = 1\%$. For neutronics, the angular moments of the flux are converged to within 1 pcm. The same value is used to bound the relative error in the multiplication factor, while a tolerance of 10 pcm is chosen for the fission integral. Note that the tolerances selected for the fuel and moderator temperatures and water density are similar to those found in literature, [9, 2].

Apart from the particular trends of the errors throughout the iterations, which are depicted in Fig. 2a, this test highlighted an unacceptable discrepancy between the two schemes in terms of power distributions, as well of the effective multiplication factor. Table I shows the magnitude of such a difference. After careful analysis of the results, we discovered that the tolerances for the water density were not sufficient to guarantee a stable converged solution when the parameter \mathcal{N} is varied. This finding is specific to the proposed high-fidelity calculation scheme, in which the moderator is not homogenised but treated in an exact way.

Contrarily to homogenized few-group cross sections, in the present scheme, the water density and boron concentration are used to set the isotopic composition of the water, which is no more smeared in the fuel and structural materials, as commonly done in standard two-step schemes. In the proposed framework, the water density is an interpolation state-parameter for microscopic cross sections of reso-

Table II. Total CPU time [min] and percentage of time spent to recompute the probability matrices and the macroscopic cross section libraries.

Calculation	Strong	Weak
Total CPU time [min]	97	115
% of CPU Time for linear MOSC coefficients	12	26
% of CPU Time for cross sections interpolation	1.7	3.9

nant isotopes and a physical parameter that allows for the re-scaling of isotopic concentrations of moderator (e.g., ^1H , ^2H , ^{16}O , ^{10}B , ^{11}B) without any approximation. Similarly the boron concentration is an interpolation state-parameter for effective microscopic cross sections and a physical parameter that allows to precisely set the boron concentration to the prescribed *ppm*.

Physical parameters related to water, in particular its density, have a noticeable impact on the macroscopic cross sections. A 1% error in the water density generates a discrepancy of 1000 *pcm* in the macroscopic cross sections, in all energy groups. The latter produces 200 *pcm* discrepancy in our results, as shown in the second column of Tab. I. Based on this observation, the tolerance for the water density has been modified to $\epsilon_{\rho_m} = 1$ *pcm*. Thanks to this modification, all schemes converge to the same solution, within the required precision, for any value of \mathcal{N} . Figure 2b shows the error in the k-eigenvalue for $\mathcal{N} = 1$ and $\mathcal{N} = 5$ for the corrected tolerance.

The last two columns of Tab. I show a difference that lies within the tolerance allowed for the iterative residual, i.e., 1 *pcm* in the reactivity and 100 *pcm* in the fission source.

To improve computational efficiency, the number of inner transport iterations was reduced to 4 RMA-accelerated one-group iterations and 4 thermal iterations within each subdomain transport calculation. This means that the operator $\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{L} - \mathcal{H}$ is only partially inverted. ‘Strong’ and ‘Weak’ converge in 27 and 45 outer iterations, respectively. The ‘Weak’ coupling tends to show large cusps at iterations with index number equal to $k \times \mathcal{N} + 1$, with $k \in \mathbb{N}^*$, due to a possible change of cross sections (and angular probability coefficients), induced by the thermal feedback, when the fission and, more particularly, the scattering source are only partially converged. The fission source error goes below 100 *pcm* (the required accuracy) in only 2 iterations, for both calculations. Concerning the simulation runtime, the reported results are obtained by OpenMP parallelism on standard Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4214 CPU @ 2.20 workstation, using 48 threads. Table II shows the total CPU time for $\mathcal{N} = 1$ and $\mathcal{N} = 5$, as well as the percentage of time spent to recompute the angular probability coefficients (IDT) and the macroscopic cross sections (XSTOOL), for each case. Finally, the time spent in the thermal-hydraulic calculation, including data processing and transfer (Python script + THEDI), amounts to few seconds, for each multiphysics iteration.

4.2. Critical boron concentration search - 17x17 UOX/B4C 3D assembly

The same precautions must be extended to the tolerance of the boron concentration. Due to Newton linearisation

$$C_B^{(\ell+1)} = C_B^{(\ell)} + \left(\frac{C_B^{(\ell)} - C_B^{(\ell-1)}}{k^{(\ell+1)} - k^{(\ell)}} \right) (k_{ref} - k^{(\ell+1)}),$$

the iterative difference $\delta C_B = C_B^{(\ell+1)} - C_B^{(\ell)}$ is directly proportional to $\delta k = k_{ref} - k^{(\ell+1)}$. To avoid unnecessary iterations between neutronics and boron concentration search, the error tolerance for boron is set to the same value used for the effective multiplication factor (see Eq. (2)), i.e., 1 *pcm* for the presented test.

The control-rod tips are now located at $z_{tip} = 370$ *cm*, so that the system, without boron, is supercritical. In the following, we search for the boron concentration that makes the system critical. The

(a) Eigenvalue error vs. outer iterations

Figure 3. 17×17 $\text{UO}_2\text{-B}_4\text{C}$ 3D lattice, with control rod tips at 370 cm, in strong coupled N-TH iterations, with critical boron concentration search

thermal-hydraulic feedback is still present, and is included at each outer iteration, by setting \mathcal{N} equal to 1. All discretization parameters are unchanged with respect to the case study analyzed in Sect. 4. The boron concentration is initialized to $C_B^{(0)} = 0.01$ ppm. The eigenvalue, fission source and inner iterations are converged to within 1 pcm, 10 pcm and 1 pcm, respectively. The boron concentration is converged to within 10 ppm, while the tolerances for the fuel temperature and the moderator density are set equal to 5°C and 1 pcm, respectively.

The k -eigenvalue converges in 33 outer iterations, showing large initial peaks, due to thermal-hydraulics and boron concentration update (Fig. 3a). In this test, the eigenvalue converges to 1 (precisely to 0,999996) to within the required tolerance of 1 pcm, and that the computed boron concentration is 514 ppm.

Concerning the simulation runtime, once again, the results are obtained by OpenMP parallel computing, with a maximum of 48 threads. The total CPU time amounts to 140 min. The fractions of time spent to recompute the angular probability coefficients and the macroscopic cross sections amount respectively to 14% and 4.2% of the total CPU time.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work investigates a novel simulation strategy for multiphysics calculations. This task has been achieved using

- The discrete-ordinate neutronics solver IDT, which projects the transport equation onto heterogeneous modular nodes, using the method of short characteristics;
- The macroscopic cross-section generator XSTOOL, performing microscopic cross-section interpolation, with (optional) subsequent energy collapse of the macroscopic cross-sections;
- The multi-1D two-phase thermal-hydraulic solver THEDI, solving energy, mass and momentum conservation in the moderator and heat conduction in the fuel pin.

The proposed numerical scheme

- does not perform cross-section homogenisation;
- is not affected by critical-leakage model error, if no flux weighting is performed to condense the macroscopic cross-sections;
- addresses all physics in the power iteration loop;
- uses the boron concentration and the moderator density both to interpolate the microscopic cross-

sections and to set the isotopic concentrations of the moderator.

Future efforts will focus on testing the presented scheme over a wide range of case studies, to confirm the preliminary numerical evidence illustrated in the present work. Comparisons with other codes are planned to establish its computational accuracy.

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